

Comparative Study of Gross Motor Skills in Athletic and Inexperienced Individuals with Down Syndrome

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Abstract:

This study examines the impact of physical and sports activities (PSA) on the gross motor skills of children with down syndrome. it compares the motor abilities of children who engage in regular physical activity to those leading a sedentary lifestyle. a structured questionnaire was administered to 150 parents. results indicate significant motor improvements in physically active children, particularly in coordination, balance, and reaction speed. the study also highlights the physiological benefits of PSA. findings confirm the value of early intervention through physical activity. motor development was influenced by both environmental stimulation and structured training. the study supports integrating PSA into therapeutic strategies for children with down syndrome.

KEY WORDS : Down Syndrome ; Motor Skills ; Gross Motor Skills.

المخلص:

تهدف هذه الدراسة إلى تحليل تأثير الأنشطة البدنية والرياضية على المهارات الحركية الكبرى لدى الأطفال المصابين بمتلازمة داون. وقد تمت مقارنة القدرات الحركية بين أطفال يمارسون النشاط البدني بانتظام وآخرين يعيشون نمطا خاملًا. تم توزيع استبيان على عينة تضم (150) ولي. أظهرت النتائج تحسنا ملحوظا في الجوانب الحركية للأطفال النشطين، خصوصا في التناسق والتوازن وسرعة الاستجابة. كما بيّنت الدراسة فوائد فسيولوجية واضحة للنشاط البدني. وأكدت النتائج أهمية التدخل المبكر من خلال ممارسة النشاط الحركي. يتأثر النمو الحركي بالتحفيز البيئي والتدريب المنظم. توصي الدراسة بدمج النشاط البدني ضمن البرامج العلاجية الموجهة للأطفال المصابين بمتلازمة داون.

الكلمات المفتاحية: متلازمة داون، المهارة الحركية، المهارة الحركية الكبرى.

1-Introduction

Down syndrome, also known as Trisomy 21, is not a disease but a congenital malformation resulting from a chromosomal abnormality. It is caused by the presence of an extra chromosome on the 21st pair, meaning that the individual with Down syndrome has 47 chromosomes instead of the usual 46. This syndrome is characterized by a cognitive impairment ranging from moderate to severe, often associated with various physical malformations (Terrier, 2008, 15). It predominantly affects a relatively young population. In children with Down syndrome, this condition stems from a chromosomal anomaly involving an extra chromosome. From another perspective, Corraze (1987) defines certain behaviors of individuals with trisomic conditions as goal-oriented actions composed of movements and postures. These movements are made possible through numerous coordinated muscle contractions that allow different parts of the body to move through space, it define their balance level (Haceini, 2024). These contractions are precisely coordinated both spatially and temporally. Movement requires more than just physical effort—it also involves perception, information processing, planning, organizing and adjusting the movement, anticipating the outcome, and controlling motor actions.

Despite having cognitive impairments, individuals with Down syndrome can achieve physical stability and cognitive development. A child with Down syndrome who is continuously learning and developing, like a neurotypical child, must exert greater mental effort. This implies the need to adapt learning methods to the child's rhythm by providing personalized tools, methods, and time—what we call the principle of individuality (Guidetti & Tourette, 2004, 2). According to Piaget, the child assimilates information from the environment and adjusts existing cognitive "schemes"—which can be motor or mental—through experience. These schemes are then modified through accommodation to adapt to new experiences (Lautrey, 2006, 20). Cognitive theories compare the brain to a computer that processes information and generates a response. Hick's (1952) experiments showed that reaction time to a light stimulus is proportional to the amount of information processed. Living beings must be capable of processing and seeking out necessary information. During motor commands, an expected effect—called the efference—is produced. The success or failure of the action is detected via sensory feedback

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known as reafference. The comparison between the intended effect and the reafference determines if the goal was achieved. The central nervous system (CNS) encodes all movement parameters: muscle group selection, intensity, contraction timing, and release. This is the motor program (Vincent, 2012, 4).

Most studies seek coherence in symptoms observed in individuals with Down syndrome, due to the syndrome's genetic consistency. However, despite some common characteristics, significant interindividual variations exist, especially in the age range during which motor skills are acquired. These variations raise questions about the interdependence of certain symptoms and their connection with other factors such as mental efficiency or specific gene localization on chromosome 21, which may influence psychomotor impairments (Sinet, 1993). Hormonal factors such as mild hypothyroidism may be linked to psychomotor stagnation, although therapeutic results in this area remain limited (Garandau, 1994). While the exact relationships among various symptoms remain hypothetical, it is necessary to analyze their influence on the development of each child. Knowledge of the psychomotor development of individuals with Down syndrome is limited due to several factors:

- Lack of longitudinal studies.
- Inconsistent assessment tools.
- Insufficient understanding of the progression and severity of symptoms over time.

Nevertheless, certain developmental characteristics are widely acknowledged. Engagement in motor activities has a significant impact on the overall development of children with Down syndrome, influencing motor, social, cognitive, and emotional domains. Physical activity can help children reach an optimal level of motor function (Corraze & Albaret, 1996).

Three key symptoms characterize the perceptual-motor profile of individuals with Trisomy 21: clumsiness, slowness in reaction and execution, and extreme variability (Sugden & Keogh, 1990). Developmental comparisons reveal that children with Down syndrome perform differently from children with general intellectual disabilities in tasks involving motor agility and locomotion—such as posture changes and movement organization (Henderson & Morris, 1981). According to Latash (1992), the slowness observed may reflect a compensatory strategy adopted by these individuals to overcome their

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difficulties in perceptual-motor decision-making. These individuals prioritize safety over efficiency.

This study focuses on “The impact of physical and sports activities (PSA) on the motor abilities of children with Down syndrome.” Some researchers regard physical activities as an effective therapeutic tool to improve motor function in children with disabilities by developing neuromuscular systems and stimulating cognitive function.

This raises a central research question: Can physical and sports activity (PSA) effectively improve motor skills in children with Down syndrome despite their cognitive impairment?

2- General objective of the study:

In this element, the objectives of the study are:

- To encourage and motivate parents of children with Down syndrome to enroll them in sports teams.
- To identify the benefits of physical and sports activities (PSA) on the gross motor skills of individuals with Down syndrome.
- To understand the pathology of Trisomy 21 and its different forms.

3- Procedural definition of the concepts mentioned in the research:

Down Syndrome (Trisomy 21): A chromosomal abnormality caused by the presence of an extra chromosome on the 21st pair. It is a genetic disorder characterized by cognitive delay and distinct morphological features.

Motor Skills: The set of neural and muscular functions that allow voluntary or automatic movements of the body.

Gross Motor Skills: The ability to perform coordinated movements involving the arms, legs, and body with a certain level of control and stability.

4- The methodological procedures used in the study:

4-1 Method and tools: the following elements are mentioned:

During our research on the comparative study of gross motor skills in novice and athletic individuals with Down syndrome, a preliminary survey conducted with a sample of ten (10) parents of children with Down syndrome enabled us to establish solid contact with educators

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working in specialized classes for individuals with intellectual disabilities (Specialized Center for Mental Disabilities, 300 Logements, Sétif), as well as swimming coaches who include individuals with Down syndrome in their training groups (Olympic Pool EL-BEZ, Sétif). These professionals willingly gave their consent to share their daily concerns related to this condition. This preliminary phase also allowed us to compute the psychometric properties of the questionnaire used in our study. The internal consistency of the questionnaire was acceptable, as indicated by a Cronbach's alpha exceeding (0.73). Additionally, the test-retest reliability demonstrated strong temporal stability, with a correlation coefficient (r) greater than (0.84).

In this study, we employed a descriptive research method, which aligns with the nature and objectives of the investigation. The research sample consisted of 150 participants, selected through non-random sampling (case study approach). All participants responded to a structured questionnaire composed of (23) closed and opened questions. The statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 21, and the Chi-square test (χ^2) was applied to examine associations between variables.

4-2 Presentation and Analysis of Results:

Table N°1: Chi-square Test Results

Item	χ^2 Calculated	χ^2 Tabulated	Level of significance	Df	Signification
1	19,44	3,84	0,05	1	*
2	74,90	3,84	0,05	1	*
3	86,64	3,84	0,05	1	*
4	1,71	3,84	0,05	1	
5	39,04	5,99	0,05	2	*
6	156,73	9,48	0,05	4	*
7	74,90	3,84	0,05	1	*
10	43,06	9,48	0,05	4	*
11	43,06	9,48	0,05	4	*

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12	86,64	3,84	0,05	1	*
13	16.66	3.84	0.05	1	*
14	40.56	7.81	0.05	3	*
15	105.84	3.84	0.05	1	*
16	10.66	3.84	0.05	1	*
17	98.22	3.84	0.05	1	*
18	99.22	3.84	0.05	1	*
19	26.44	5.99	0.05	2	*
20	51.24	5.99	0.05	2	*
21	109.22	3.84	0.05	1	*
22	72.11	8.84	0.05	1	*
23	80.66	8.84	0.05	1	*

4-3 Discussion and interpretation of the results:

Before beginning this discussion, it is useful to recall that the general research question posed at the start of this study was the following:

Is there really an improvement in the motor aspect among children with Down syndrome who practice physical and sports activities (PSA), knowing the existence of a cognitive disability?

To answer this question, we formulated a general hypothesis suggesting that there is an improvement in the motor aspect among children with Down syndrome who engage in PSA, despite their cognitive disability. The secondary hypotheses are as follows:

The first suggests that PSA meets the needs of gross motor skills (GMS) in children with Down syndrome.

The second proposes that PSA contributes to the development of the physiological system in these children.

According to the results obtained from our survey, it is confirmed that there is an improvement in the motor aspect in children with Down syndrome who practice PSA, despite their cognitive disability. The responses from their parents to the questionnaire indicate noticeable motor improvements.

The first partial hypothesis suggests that PSA meets the needs of gross motor skills in children with Down syndrome. This assumption is validated, as most parental responses to the 12 questions in the first section of the questionnaire (which contains 150 items in total) demonstrate that PSA improves the motor system of these children.

We relied on the study by Sachet (2013) titled "Reflection on the management of gross motor skills in two children with Down syndrome", which confirms through its results that PSA leads to:

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- Progress in general dynamic coordination,
- Reduced fatigue,
- Less frequent balance issues,
- Improved behavior,
- Adaptation and reflection on psychomotor rehabilitation strategies—although there is limited feedback on the effectiveness of these adaptations.

We also relied on Beaulieu's study (2000), titled “Comparison of psychomotor development in children aged 3 to 5 attending or not attending a daycare with a psychomotor education program”, conducted at the University of Quebec at Trois-Rivières. This study supports the hypothesis in part. At the end of the program, children attending the daycare—with stimulation from a psychomotor education program—achieved significantly better performances in all components of gross motor skills than children who stayed at home. These results confirm Rigal's (1996) hypothesis, which states that performance levels achieved after training are higher than those reached through maturation alone. Indeed, all post-test scores in the experimental group were higher than those of the control group, particularly in balance, locomotor, non-locomotor, and manipulation skills. Overall, the results from gross motor skill assessments confirm that the practice of psychomotor activities has a marked influence on children's motor development. These results support the hypotheses proposed by various authors in the motor domain. Motor activity has a significant impact on child development. It affects all aspects of a child's overall development—motor, social, cognitive, and emotional—according to authors such as Le Bouch (1984), Lauzon (1990), De Lièvre & Staes (1993), Epstein (1993), Schweinhart, Barnes & Weikart (1993), Ignico (1994), Rigal (1996), Bolduc (1997), Paoletti (1996), and Pica (1999). Motor activity helps children reach optimal performance levels in their motor functions. In fact, it is well-established that performance achieved after training exceeds that attained by maturation alone (Rigal, 1996). Physical activity also has beneficial effects on the health of children with Down syndrome, particularly on body composition, physical condition, bone metabolism, mental health, and lipid profiles. Although the benefits are significant, the most important aspect is to establish a lasting habit and interest in physical activity that continues throughout life. Ultimately, the goal of promoting physical activity in young children

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with Down syndrome is to help them develop intellectual and behavioral abilities, encouraging them to adopt an active lifestyle for life (Duché & Van Praagh, 2009).

The second hypothesis suggests that PSA contributes to the development of the physiological system in children with Down syndrome. This is confirmed by the parents' responses to the 11 questions in the second section of the questionnaire, which show that PSA has a developmental effect on the physiological system of their children. We referred to the research of Vincent (2012), titled "Example of gross motor skills management based on the training of developmental motor stages". The hypothesis of this study posits that training coordination patterns present in development can help install and/or stabilize certain motor skills. The results, although not massive, show some improvements—especially in posture, stability, and movement fluidity. Intellectual disability does not define the full extent of a person's difficulties. Its expression can vary widely and is often associated with various other conditions. We also referred to the local study by Seddiki and Tighremt (2017) titled "Early education for children with Down syndrome". This study examined whether early education at the psychopedagogical center in Bejaia meets the medical, psychomotor, speech therapy, educational, and psychological needs of children with Down syndrome.

The findings revealed:

- Early education at the center does not meet the psychomotor, speech therapy, or psychological needs because 1-Psychomotor aspect: Only one sport session per week without a trained coach; the educator substitutes. 2-Speech therapy: Lack of speech therapists results in poor care. 3-Psychological: Although each child has a psychological file, there is no regular follow-up.

- Early education does meet the medical and educational needs:

1-Medical: Each child has a medical file and receives follow-up. 2-Educational: Educators focus on promoting autonomy and teaching basic daily life skills, including handling speech therapy and psychomotor tasks themselves. Researchers observed that early education at the center addresses only two needs—medical and educational—while neglecting the others.

Gross motor development in children is important for several reasons: First, it allows the child to develop fundamental locomotor skills (crawling, walking, running) and object control (grasping,

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manipulating, using tools), enabling exploration and interaction with their environment. Second, it refines body control (muscle tone, posture, coordination of body segments), in both gross and fine motor activities. Third, motor development influences other domains: emotional (through autonomy), intellectual (through environmental exploration), and social (through play and interaction with peers) (Haywood & Getchell, 2002).

The importance of age-related motor development and environmental stimulation is widely recognized (Newell, 1984; Seefeldt, 1980; Rigal, 1996; Wall, 2004). Some aspects of this development (body schema, spatial and temporal structuring) are considered essential prerequisites for school learning (Lauzon, 1990; Rigal, 1996; De Lièvre & Staes, 2000). A child with underdeveloped motor skills may experience learning difficulties from the very beginning of schooling (Connor-Kuntz & Dummer, 1996). In conclusion, based on the questionnaire results and confirmation of the secondary hypotheses, we can say that there is indeed an improvement in the motor aspect among children with Down syndrome who practice PSA despite their cognitive disability.

From our work, we concluded that:

PSA has a positive effect on gross motor skills in children with Down syndrome, which inevitably leads to the development of their motor abilities.

PSA contributes to the development of reaction speed in these children.

PSA plays a role in the development of their physiological system, including muscular development and body morphology.

PSA supports the development of reflexes in children with Down syndrome.

Conclusion:

The starting point of this study focuses on the practice of physical and sports activities (PSAs) and motor skills, with the aim of promoting motor and physiological development in children with Down syndrome, as a state of physical well-being. Regular physical activity among children with Down syndrome is considered one of the key factors influencing their ability to perform routine movements in daily life. Our study is structured into three main parts: the introductory section, the theoretical part, and the practical part. Through our

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literature review and fieldwork, we chose to address a problem centered on a comparative study between children with Down syndrome who practice physical activity and those who lead a sedentary lifestyle. To do so, we developed a questionnaire aimed at verifying our hypotheses. In the introductory section, we presented the problem of our study and the corresponding hypotheses. The second part, which is theoretical, is divided into two chapters. The first chapter discusses Down syndrome: its definition, historical background, forms, characteristics, etc. The second and final chapter includes information about gross motor skills, their definition, characteristics, and motor abilities. The third part is the practical section. After presenting our research procedures, we created a questionnaire composed of two axes. The first axis: PSAs meet the needs of gross motor skills in children with Down syndrome. This section consists of 12 questions. The second axis: PSAs contribute to the development of the physiological system in children with Down syndrome. This section consists of 11 questions. Based on the results obtained from the questionnaire, we concluded the following:

- PSAs have a positive effect on the gross motor skills of children with Down syndrome.
- PSAs contribute to the development of the physiological system in children with Down syndrome.

This study is a modest attempt, limited by the materials available. Nonetheless, we aim to provide a starting point for further research in this underexplored area.

The results of this research clearly demonstrate the importance of practicing PSAs to improve the motor abilities of children with Down syndrome, even in the presence of cognitive disabilities.

Based on this, several suggestions and recommendations can be made for parents of children with Down syndrome:

- Enroll children with Down syndrome in sports clubs from an early age.
- Choose coaches and educators specialized in working with children with Down syndrome.
- Encourage them to regularly participate in household tasks as a form of motor activity.
- Enroll children in simple and accessible sports, and above all, allow them to practice the physical activities they enjoy.

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